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AUTOMATIC SENSOR BASED WALL PAINTING ROBOT

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Abstract:

Wall painting is a repetitive, exhausting and hazardous process which makes it an ideal case for automation. Painting had been automated in automotive industry but not yet for the construction industry. There is a strong need for a mobile robot that can move to paint interior walls of residential buildings. In this paper, the conceptual design of an autonomous wall painting robot is described consisting of an arm that scans the walls vertically and is fitted on a mobile robot base to give the lateral feed motion to cover the painting area. The design objective is to satisfy the criteria of simplicity, low weight, low cost and fast painting time. Ultrasonic sensors are fitted on the arm and the mobile base to adjust the motion limits and maneuver in the room area .A control system is designed to guide the arm motion and plan the mobile base motion

Key words: Automatic, wall painting, Robot, Sensor

1. INTRODUCTION

Building and construction is one of the major industries around the world. In this fast moving life construction industry is also growing rapidly. But the labours in the construction industry are not sufficient. This insufficient labours in the construction industry is because of the difficulty in the work. In construction industry, during the work in tall buildings or in the sites where there is more risky situation like interior area in the city. There are some other reasons for the insufficient labour which may be because of the improvement the education level which cause the people to think that these types of work is not as prestigious as the other jobs. The construction industry is labour-intensive and conducted in dangerous situations; therefore the importance of construction robotics has been realized and is grown rapidly. Applications and activities of robotics and automation in this construction industry started in the early 90's aiming to optimize equipment operations, improve safety, enhance perception of workspace and furthermore, ensure quality environment for building occupant. After this, the advances in the robotics and automation in the construction industry has grown rapidly.

2. EXISTING AUTOMATED WALL-PAINTING ROBOT

Warszawsky and Kahane , developed a robot for interior finishing tasks named "TAMIR", and was used in four interior finishing tasks namely; painting, plastering, tiling and masonry. The robot has 6 DOF (Degrees Of

Freedom) with an average reach of 1.7m and end effector payload of 30 kg. It is mounted on 3 wheeled mobile-robot which gives another 3 DOF. The platform moves between workstations and at each one it deploys four stabilizing legs. The robot arm used is the S-700 model made by General Motors, of 500 Kg weight.

A scaled down robot setup for interior wall painting together with a multicolour spraying end tool were implemented by Naticchia and claimed to work in full scale without reduction in performance. The robot named "Pollock#1" had 6 DOF, a nominal reach of 0.4 m and a maximum payload of 4kg. It should be fixed on a 2 DOF hexapod for horizontal movement but was not actually used in experiments. A full scale mechanism for ceil painting was introduced by aris. It had 3DOF without considering those of the platform, a working envelope of (84cm by 72 cm by 122 cm).

3. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram gives a brief idea about various important parts of the wall painting robot. Here the important parts are controller, motor, battery, sprayer, micro controller, IR sensors, keypad. Micro controller is brain of the system which will control the entire system in response to the instructions from the keypad and sensor controller through receiver. Battery is the power supply for the system which is chooses based on the sprayer timing and the system's average current. Four motors are used to motion of automatic wall painting robot. The spraying part is arranged with a sprayer gun, geared motor.

Figure 1 Block diagram

4. MICROCONTROLLER (ATMEGA 328 P)

The high-performance Atmel 8-bit AVR RISC-based microcontroller combines 32 KB ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 1 KB EEPROM, 2 KB SRAM, 23 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, three flexible timer/counters with compare modes, internal and external interrupts, serial programmable USART, a byte-oriented 2-wire serial interface, SPI serial port, 6-channel 10-bit A/D converter (8-channels in TQFP and QFN/MLF packages), programmable watchdog timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power

saving modes. The device operates between 1.8-5.5 volts. By executing powerful instructions in a single clock cycle, the device achieves throughputs approaching 1 MIPS per MHz, balancing power consumption and processing speed.

Figure 2 At mega 328 P

Today the ATmega328 is commonly used in many projects and autonomous systems where a simple, low-powered, low-cost micro-controller is needed. Perhaps the most common implementation of this chip is on the ever popular Arduino development platform, namely the Arduino Uno and Arduino Nano models.

5. IR SENSOR

An infrared sensor is an electronic device ,that emits in order to sense some aspects of the surroundings. An IR sensor can measure the heat of an object as well as detects the motion .These types of sensors measures only infrared radiation, rather than emitting it that is called as a passive IR sensor. Usually in the infrared spectrum, all the objects radiate some form of thermal radiations. These types of radiations are invisible to our eyes, that can be detected by an infrared sensor .The emitter is simply an IR LED (Light Emitting Diode) and the detector is simply an IR photodiode which is sensitive to IR light of the same wavelength as that emitted by the IR LED. When IR light falls on the photodiode, the resistances and these output voltages, change in proportion to the magnitude of the IR light received.

Figure 3 IR Sensor

5.1 PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

We have already discussed how a light sensor works. IR Sensors work by using a specific light sensor to detect a select light wavelength in the Infra-Red (IR) spectrum. By using an LED which produces light at the same wavelength as what the sensor is looking for, you can look at the intensity of the received light. When an object is close to the sensor, the light from the LED bounces off the object and into the light sensor. This results in a large jump in the intensity, which we already know can be detected using a threshold.

Since the sensor works by looking for reflected light, it is possible to have a sensor that can return the value of the reflected light. This type of sensor can then be used to measure how "bright" the object is. This is useful for tasks like line tracking.

Figure 4 Working On Object

Figure 5 Working On Reflected Light

6. LIQUID CRYSTAL DISPLAY (LCD)

LCD (liquid crystal display) is the technology used for displays in notebook and other smaller computers. Like light-emitting diode and gas-plasma technologies, LCDs allow displays to be much thinner than cathode ray tube technology. LCDs consume much less power than LED and gas-display displays because they work on the principle of blocking light rather than emitting it. An LCD is made with either a passive matrix or an active matrix display grid. The active matrix LCD is also known as a thin film transistor display. The passive matrix LCD has a grid of conductors with pixels located at each intersection in the grid. A current is sent across two conductors on the grid to control the light for any pixel. An active matrix has a transistor located at each pixel intersection, requiring less current to control the luminance of a pixel. For this reason, the current in an active matrix display can be switched

on and off more frequently, improving the screen refresh time. When electric charge is applied they align to block the light entering through them, whereas when no-charge is applied they become transparent. Light cursory through makes the desired images appear. This is the basic concept behind LCD displays. LCDs are most generally used because of their advantages over other display technologies. They are thin and flat and deplete very small amount of power compared to LED displays and cathode ray tubes (CRTs).

Figure 6 LCD Display

7. MOTOR DRIVERS

A motor driver IC is an integrated circuit chip which is usually used to control motors in autonomous robots. Motor driver ICs act as an interface between microcontroller in robots and the motors in the robot. The most commonly used motor driver IC's are from the L293 series such as, L293NE, etc. These ICs are designed to control 2 DC motors simultaneously. L293D consist of two H-bridge. H-bridge is the simplest circuit for controlling a low current rated motor. For this tutorial we will be referring the motor driver IC as L293D only.

Figure 7 IC L293D

8. SPRAYER

Spray painting is a painting technique where a device sprays a coating (paint, ink, varnish, etc.) through the air onto a surface. The most common types employ compressed gas usually air to atomize and direct the paint particles. Spray guns evolved from airbrushes, and the two are usually distinguished by their size and the size of the spray pattern they produce. Airbrushes are hand-held and used instead of a brush for detailed work such as photo retouching, painting nails or fine art. Air gun spraying uses equipment that is generally larger. It is typically used for covering large surfaces with an even coating of liquid. Spray guns can be either automated or hand-held and have interchangeable heads to allow for different spray patterns. Single color aerosol paint cans are portable and easy to store.

Figure 8 Sprayer

9. WORKING OF WALL PAINTING ROBOT

Set the distance of wall in control unit of the robot with Keypad interface. Initially the robot start from right then up down tower mechanism is active and the sprayer unit move up and down with air pressure through nozzle to clean the wall. Then load the sprayer fill with paint and activate robot from right side then sprayer section moves to left till distance reached and after a unit up movement and robot move to right and the process repeats. The distance moved by robot is measured using IR sensor connected on the Wheel of the Robot.

Figure 9 Basic Model

10. CONCLUSION

We have studied well about the project work of Automatic Sensor Based Wall Painting Robot. We wish to complete this project in section wise. As the first step by taking some approximate measures we designed a Painting Robot structure and components to be used and their ratings. After that for choosing the main component geared motor is depended up on the net weight of the system. By taking approximate weights we choose the motor rating. to initiate this project's hardware in the seventh semester ,we fabricated the frame for the wall painting robot. The remaining works of the project will be done in the eighth semester. It includes the purchasing of the components, its testing, designing, make practice for its painting.

11. ADVANTAGES

Our proposed project has higher efficiency and better productivity. It also has increased labours safety. Then the power consumption rate is very low. And in the project we have also minimised the use of paint. Moreover our unit have higher consistency.

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